

Synthesis of Quaternary Salts of Ammonia from Aromatic Compounds through the Formation of Glycidyl Ether and their Plant Growth Retardant Activity

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In continuation of our work on the synthesis and growth-retarding activity of trialkylammonium compounds¹, we have studied eight new trialkylammonium compounds containing propanolic and oximinopropanolic chains linked to aromatic nucleus. These compounds may be useful in agriculture for bud and seed dormancy and preventing growth of wide range of pathogens.

Phenol, salicylaldehyde and α -naphthol (1a-c) separately on treatment with epichlorohydrin produced a mixture of 2,3-epoxypropyloxy (2a-c)² and 3-chloro-2-hydroxypropyloxy (3a-c)³ derivatives. This mixture on reaction with diethylamine² produced 3-diethylamino-2-hydroxypropyloxy derivatives (4a-c). 1-(3-Diethylamino-2-hydroxypropyloximino)-1-phenylethane (9) was prepared by refluxing the epoxide (8) with diethylamine in methanol⁴, which in turn was procured by the epoxypropylation of

acetophenone oxime (7). The tertiary amines (4a-c and 9) were then reacted with ethyl bromide and methyl iodide separately to get the quaternary salts of ammonia (5a-c, 6a-c, 10 and 11). These salts were tested as plant growth retardants on turnip seeds⁵ (Table 1). All the salts showed plant growth retardant activity but less than that of abscisic acid (ABA). Compounds 6b, 6c and 11 showed comparatively high plant growth retardant activity at higher concentrations.

Experimental

B.ps. are uncorrected. ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃/CCl₄) were recorded on a EM-390/360 spectrometer using TMS as internal standard and ir spectra on a Perkin-Elmer 800 spectrophotometer. The homogeneity of compounds was routinely checked on silica gel tlc plates.

(3-Diethylamino-2-hydroxypropyloxy) derivatives of aromatic compounds (4a-c): Phenol (1a-c; 90 mmol) was dissolved in aqueous 7% KOH (90 ml) and epichlorohydrin (9 ml) was added dropwise with constant stirring at 10–15°. The stirring was continued for 36 h at room temperature. The separated oil was then extracted with benzene, washed with 10% NaOH and finally with water. Removal of benzene from the dried extract followed by distillation under reduced pressure of the residual oil, afforded a mixture of 2a-c and 3a-c (tlc showed two spots), which was used as such in the next step. The above mixture (2 g) and diethylamine (1 g) were refluxed together in absolute ethanol (30 ml) for 4 h, then cooled and alcohol distilled off. The residual oil was distilled under reduced pressure to yield the product: 4a, (17.8 g, 85%), b.p. 180–182°/8–9 mm (Found: C, 69.82; H, 9.33; N, 6.4. C₁₃H₂₁NO₂ calcd. for: C, 69.96; H, 9.42; N, 6.28%; ν_{max} (neat) 3450 cm⁻¹ (OH); δ 1.05 (6H, t, J 7 Hz, N(CH₂CH₃)₂), 2.65 (6H, m, CH₂N(CH₂CH₃)₂), 4.05 (3H, bs, CHOH, OCH₂), 4.55 (1H, b s, OH), 6.6–7.7 (5H, ArH); 4b, (8.6 g, 38%), 110–13°/4–5mm (Found: C, 66.72; H, 8.56; N, 5.4. C₁₄H₂₁NO₃ calcd. for: C, 66.93; H, 8.37; N, 5.58%; ν_{max} (neat) 3450 cm⁻¹ (OH); δ 1.03 (6H, t, J 7 Hz, N(CH₂CH₃)₂), 2.65 (6H, m, CH₂N(CH₂CH₃)₂), 4.0 (3H, b s, OCH₂, CHOH), 4.3 (1H, b s, OH), 6.7–7.7 (4H, ArH); 4c (15.7 g, 64%), 230–32°/7–8 mm (Found: C, 54.42; H, 6.3; N, 3.90. C₁₇H₂₃NO₂ calcd. for: C, 54.69; H, 6.17; N, 3.75%; ν_{max} (neat) 3450 cm⁻¹ (OH); δ 1.03 (6H, t, J 7 Hz, N(CH₂CH₃)₂), 2.65 (6H, m,

TABLE I—PLANT GROWTH RETARDANT ACTIVITY IN DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS (mg dm⁻³) OF THE COMPOUNDS

Compound	% Germination (Average 50 seeds)				Average length of seedlings (cm)			
	10	25	50	100	10	25	50	100
5a	82	74	66	58	0.97	0.88	0.76	0.63
6a	85.5	80	77.5	74	0.97	0.81	0.71	0.62
5b	86	76	71	59	1.11	0.79	0.66	0.61
6b	80	70	58	46	0.81	0.73	0.55	0.44
5c	90	82	74	71	1.19	0.90	0.77	0.72
6c	87	81	67	39	0.92	0.79	0.36	0.16
10	91	85	78	55	1.21	0.89	0.78	0.69
11	82.5	78.5	62	47	1.094	0.906	0.686	0.39
	% of Germination				Av. length of seedlings (cm)			
	ABA (5 ppm)		16%		0.342 cm			
	Water		100%		1.77 cm			

CH₂N(CH₂CH₃)₂, 4.16 (3H, b s, OCH₂, CHOH), 4.5 (1H, b s, OH), 6.8–8.6 (7H, m, ArH).

1-(2,3-Epoxypropyloximino-1-phenylethane (8)) : To a stirred solution of acetophenoneoxime (7.5 g) in dry acetone (150 ml), powdered KOH (6.2 g) was added in three lots at room temperature. After the separation of salt, epichlorohydrin (6.7 ml) was added dropwise and stirring continued for 24 h. The excess of acetone and epichlorohydrin were then removed by distillation and the residue was taken in ether, washed with water and saturated NaCl solution. The dried extract was concentrated and distilled under reduced pressure to give **8** (5.1 g, 80%), b.p. 180–82°/7–8 mm (Found : C, 69.26; H, 6.95; N, 7.15. C₁₁H₁₃NO₂ calcd. for : C, 69.11; H, 6.8; N, 7.33%); ν_{\max} (neat) 1 620 (C=N), and 910 cm⁻¹ (epoxide);

δ 2.15 (3H, s, Ar(C=)CH₃), 2.5 (2H, m,) , 3.1 (1H,

(1H, s,) , 7.15–7.75 (5H, ArH).

1-(3-Diethylamino-2-hydroxypropyloximino)-1-phenylethane (9) : A mixture of the epoxide (8.2 g) and diethylamine (1.5 g) was refluxed in methanol for 5 h. Methanol was then distilled off and the residue taken up in ether. The organic phase was washed with water and saturated NaCl solution successively and dried. Removal of the solvent followed by vacuum distillation afforded the product as a thick oil (2.4 g, 90%), b.p. 170–72°/5–6 mm (Found : C, 68.02; H, 9.23; N, 10.81. C₁₅H₂₄N₂O₂ calcd. for : C, 68.18; H, 9.09; N, 10.6%); ν_{\max} (neat) 3 400 (OH) and 1 620 cm⁻¹ (C=N); δ 1.04 (6H, t, J 7 Hz,

N(CH₂CH₃)₂, 2.25 (3H, s, Ar(C=)CH₃), 2.6 (6H, m, CH₂N(CH₂CH₃)₂) 3.15 (1H, s, CHOH), 4.1 (3H, b s, OCH₂, CHOH), 7.25–7.65 (5H, ArH).

Quaternary salts. General procedure : A mixture of **9** (500 mg) dissolved in dry acetone (10 ml) and alkyl halide (3 ml) was refluxed on a water-bath for 4 h. Removal of the solvent afforded quaternary salts of ammonia. Except **5b** which was hygroscopic thick liquid, other salts were obtained as thick oil (yields 60–90%).

Biological evaluation : Fifty seeds of turnip (*Brassica rapa* Var. L) in three replications were placed on a filter paper laid on a petridish to which the test solutions (5 ml) of different concentrations (10, 25, 50 and 100 ppm) of compounds were added. Each dish was kept at 28 ± 1° for 60 h and then the percent seed germination and seedling length were recorded. Separate control experiments with abscisic acid (concentration 5 ppm) and water were also performed.

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